

Augmentation of Heat transfer for non-Newtonian fluid using screw Heat Exchanger

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ABSTRACT

Heat exchangers have several industrial and engineering applications. The design procedure of heat exchangers is quite complicated, as it needs exact analysis of heat transfer rate and pressure drop estimations apart from issues such as long-term performance and the economic aspect of the equipment. Whenever inserts are used for the heat transfer enhancement, along with the increase in the heat transfer rate, the pressure drop also varies. This variation in pressure drop varies the pumping cost. Therefore any augmentation device should optimize between the benefits due to the increased heat transfer coefficient and the higher cost involved because of the increased frictional losses. Heat transfer augmentation techniques (passive, active or a combination of passive and active methods) are commonly used in areas such as process industries, heating and cooling in evaporators, thermal power plants, air-conditioning equipment, refrigerators, radiators for space vehicles, automobiles, etc. Passive techniques, where inserts are used in the flow passage to augment the heat transfer rate, are advantageous compared with active techniques, because the insert manufacturing process is simple and these techniques can be easily employed in an existing heat exchanger.

Keyword: Active Technique, Passive Technique, Compound Technique, Heat exchanger for non-Newtonian fluid

INTRODUCTION

Heat exchangers have several industrial and engineering applications. The design procedure of heat exchangers is quite complicated, as it needs exact analysis of heat transfer rate and pressure drop estimations apart from issues such as long-term performance and the economic aspect of the equipment. To make the equipment compact and achieve a high heat transfer rate using minimum pumping power.

Techniques for heat transfer augmentation are relevant to several engineering applications. In recent years, the high cost of energy and material has resulted in an increased effort aimed at producing more efficient heat exchange equipment.

Furthermore, sometimes there is a need for miniaturization of a heat exchanger in specific applications, such as space application, through an augmentation of heat transfer. Therefore, an increase in the efficiency of the heat exchanger through an augmentation technique may result in a considerable saving in the material cost. In some specific applications, such as heat exchangers dealing with fluids of low thermal conductivity (gases and oils) and desalination plants, there is a need to Increase the heat transfer rate. The heat transfer rate can be improved by introducing a disturbance in the fluid flow (breaking the viscous and thermal boundary layers), but in the process pumping power may increase significantly and ultimately the pumping cost becomes high. Therefore, to achieve a desired heat transfer rate in an existing heat exchanger at an economic pumping power, several techniques have been proposed in recent years and are discussed in the following sections.

HEAT TRANSFER AUGMENTATION

Passive Techniques: These techniques do not require any direct input of external power; rather they use it from the system itself which ultimately leads to an increase in fluid pressure drop. They

generally use surface or geometrical modifications to the flow channel by incorporating inserts or additional devices. They promote higher heat transfer coefficients by disturbing or altering the existing flow behavior except for extended surfaces. Heat transfer augmentation by these techniques can be achieved by using;

Treated Surfaces: Such surfaces have a fine scale alteration to their finish or coating which may be continuous or discontinuous. They are primarily used for boiling and condensing duties.

Rough surfaces: These are the surface modifications that promote turbulence in the flow field in the wall region, primarily in single phase flows, without increase in heat transfer surface area.

Extended surfaces: They provide effective heat transfer enlargement. The newer developments have led to modified finned surfaces that also tend to improve the heat transfer coefficients by disturbing the flow field in addition to increasing the surface area.

Displaced enhancement devices: These are the inserts that are used primarily in confined forced convection, and they improve energy transport indirectly at the heat exchange surface by displacing the fluid from the heated or cooled surface of the duct with bulk fluid from the core flow.

Swirl flow devices: They produce and superimpose swirl flow or secondary recirculation on the axial flow in a channel. These include helical strip or cored screw type tube inserts, twisted tapes. They can be used for single phase and two-phase flows.

Coiled tubes: These lead to relatively more compact heat exchangers. It produces secondary flows and vortices which promote higher heat transfer coefficients in single phase flows as well as in most regions of boiling.

Surface tension devices: These consist of wicking or grooved surfaces, which direct and improve the flow of liquid to boiling surfaces and from condensing surfaces.

Additives for liquids: These include the addition of solid particles, soluble trace additives and gas bubbles in single phase flows and trace additives which usually depress the surface tension of the liquid for boiling systems.

Additives for gases: These include liquid droplets or solid particles, which are introduced in single-phase gas flows either as dilute phase (gas-solid suspensions) or as dense phase (fluidized beds).

Active Techniques:

In these cases, external power is used to facilitate the desired flow modification and the concomitant improvement in the rate of heat transfer.

Augmentation of heat transfer by this method can be achieved by Mechanical Aids: Such instruments stir the fluid by mechanical means or by rotating the surface. These include rotating tube heat exchangers and scrapped surface heat and mass exchangers.

Surface vibration: They have been applied in single phase flows to obtain higher heat transfer coefficients.

Fluid vibration: These are primarily used in single phase flows and are considered to be perhaps the most practical type of vibration enhancement technique.

Electrostatic fields: It can be in the form of electric or magnetic fields or a combination of the two from dc or ac sources, which can be applied in heat exchange systems involving dielectric fluids. Depending on the application, it can also produce greater bulk mixing and induce forced convection or electromagnetic pumping to enhance heat transfer.

Injection: Such a technique is used in single phase flow and pertains to the method of injecting the same or a different fluid into the main bulk fluid either through a porous heat transfer interface or upstream of the heat transfer section.

Suction: It involves either vapor removal through a porous heated surface in nucleate or film boiling, or fluid withdrawal through a porous heated surface in single-phase flow.

Jet impingement: It involves the direction of heating or cooling fluid perpendicularly or obliquely to the heat transfer surface.

Compound Techniques:

When any two or more of these techniques are employed simultaneously to obtain enhancement in heat transfer that is greater than that produced by either of them when used individually, is termed as compound enhancement. This technique involves complex design and hence has limited applications.

Compound techniques are slowly emerging area of enhancement that hold promise for practical applications, since heat transfer coefficients can usually be increased above each of the several techniques acting alone. Some examples that have been studied are as follows:

- ❖ Rough tube wall with twisted-tape inserts
- ❖ Rough cylinder with acoustic vibrations
- ❖ Internally finned tube with twisted-tape insert
- ❖ Finned tubes in fluidized beds
- ❖ Externally finned tubes subjected to vibrations
- ❖ Rib-roughened passage being rotated
- ❖ Gas-solid suspension with an electrical field
- ❖ Fluidized bed with pulsations of air
- ❖ Rib-roughened channel with longitudinal vortex regeneration.

One may consider the use of augmentation techniques to satisfy any of the following thermal-hydraulic objectives: (1) to reduce

prime surface area, (2) to increase heat transfer capacity, (3) to reduce the approach temperature difference for the process streams, or (4) to reduce pumping power.

Some of important surfaces which are used commonly in augmentation of heat transfer are discussed below

TREATED SURFACES:

These are primarily applicable in two phase heat transfer and they consist of a variety of structured surfaces (continuous or discontinuous integral surface roughness or alterations) and coatings. Though the treatment provides a roughness to the surface, it is not large enough to influence single phase heat transfer.

Boiling: Different types of treated surfaces used are

- ❖ Machined or grooved surfaces
- ❖ Formed or modified low-fin surfaces
- ❖ Multilayered surfaces
- ❖ Coated surfaces

The principle of providing treated surfaces for enhanced boiling is to produce a large number of stable vapor traps or nucleation sites on the surface. This is applicable for highly wetting fluids like refrigerants, organic liquids, cryogenics and alkali liquid metals where the normal cavities present on the heated surfaces tend to experience sub-cooled liquid flooding. For less wetting or relatively higher surface tension fluids, coatings of non-wetting material (eg.teflon) on either the heated surface or its pits and cavities have been found to improve stable nucleation and reduce the required wall super

When the stainless steel surface along with Teflon is spread to create spots of the no-wetting material on the heated surface it was found to promote nucleate boiling in water with relatively low wall super heat and three to four times higher heat transfer coefficients, was proposed by Young and Hummel(1965). In a more recent study of boiling of alcohols (methanol, ethanol and isopropanol) at atmospheric and sub-atmospheric pressures on a horizontal brass tube coated with poly-tetra-fluoro-ethylene (PTFE), Vijaya Vittala et al. (2001), found a significant enhancement in heat transfer.

ROUGH SURFACES:

Single Phase Flow:

The use of surface roughness in turbulent single phase flow is one of the simplest and highly effective techniques; small scale roughness has little effect in laminar flows. It essentially disturbs the viscous laminar sub-layer near the wall to promote higher momentum and heat transport. Surface roughness can be introduced in the form of wire-coiled type inserts or it may be integral to the surface.

Rough surfaces have been employed to enhance heat transfer in single phase flows both inside tubes and outside tubes. Dong et al. (2001) developed a new set of analogy based friction factor and Nusselt number correlations for turbulent flows of water and oil in spirally corrugated tubes.

DISPLACED ENHANCEMENT DEVICES:

Single-Phase Flow: Several types of inserts which are categorized as displaced enhancement devices include static mixer elements (e.g. Kenics, Sulzer), metallic mesh, discs, wire matrix inserts, rings or balls which tend to displace the fluid from the core of the channel to its heated or cooled wall and vice versa, keeping the heat transfer surface unaltered. Rings and round balls have comparable heat transfer improvements, but the friction factors are exorbitantly high. Most of the devices are effective

only in laminar flows, as in turbulent flows, the pressure drop penalties are extremely high as reported by Bergles (1998).

Fig. 1 : Conical Ring inserts in circular tubes.

a:- Diverging Ring

b:- Converging Ring

c:- Converging and Diverging Rings

SWIRL FLOW DEVICES:

Swirl flow devices generally consist of a variety of tube inserts, geometrically varied flow arrangements and duct geometry modifications that produce flows. These techniques include twisted tape inserts, periodic tangential fluid injection and helically twisted tubes.

Fig 2 : Example of (a) full-length twisted tape, (b) regularly spaced twisted tape and (c) smoothly varying (gradually decreasing) pitch full-length twisted tape

Single-Phase flows:

Twisted tape inserts are the most widely used swirl flow device for single-phase flows. These inserts increase the heat transfer coefficient significantly with a relatively small pressure drop penalty as reported by Smithberg and Landis (1964); Lopina and

Bergles (1969); Date and Singham (1972); Manglik and Bergles (1992); Manglik and Yera (2002). Twisted tapes can be used in the existing shell and tube heat exchangers to upgrade their heat duties or when employed in a new exchanger for a specified heat duty, significant reduction in size can be achieved. They developed empirical equations for Nusselt number and friction factor:

$$Nu = 0.258 (Re)^{0.254} (Pr) (Y)^{-0.242} (1+S/Dh)^{-0.042}$$

$$f = (Re)^{-0.384} (Y)^{-0.852} (1+S/Dh)^{-0.047}$$

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The setup of heat exchanger is used for experimentation purpose. The setup was suitable for the glycerol as a working fluid.

The basic idea for experimental is taken from Omkar Shewale's thesis.

Specifications--

Inner pipe ID = 22mm

Inner pipe OD=25mm

Outer pipe ID =53mm

Outer pipe OD=61mm

Heat transfer length= 2.43m

The experiments are performed on the setup by keeping the flow rate of fluid flowing through the outer tube constant and the flow rate of fluid flowing through the inner tube is varied. The water is used as cold fluid flowing through inner tube and glycerol is used as hot fluid flowing through outer tube. Two heaters are used for heating the glycerol.

Experimental Procedure:

- i. Heaters are switched "ON" and fluid i.e. glycerol is heated to required temperature for 1 hour approximately.
- ii. After achieving the desired temperature level of the hot fluid, valve of the cold fluid i.e. water is opened. The flow of cold water is adjusted by using the valve and rotameter which is calibrated for water.
- iii. Gear pump is switched "ON" to circulate the glycerol and flow rate is adjusted by using the ball valve and by-pass valve arrangement provided to the pump assembly also rotameter which is calibrated for glycerol is used.
- iv. Inlet and outlet temperatures of hot and cold fluids are recorded at the interval of 15 minutes till the steady state is reached.
- v. After completion of first set of readings, the procedure is repeated for the different flow rate of the cold fluid.
- vi. This experimentation is repeated for various speeds of D.C. motor viz. 0, 75, 150, 225, 300. To change speed of motor control circuit is used.

SAMPLE CALCULATIONS

Pressure Drop, Heat transfer and Friction Factor Calculation-

$$Ac = \pi/4 \times d_i^2$$

$$V = m / (Ac \times \rho_w)$$

$$\Delta P = (\rho_{ccl4} - \rho_w) \times g \times h$$

$$f_a = \Delta P \times d_i / (2 \times \rho \times L_p \times V^2)$$

$$\mu = 0.85 \text{ cP}$$

$$Re = 4 \times m / (\pi \times d_i \times \mu)$$

$$f_o = 0.046 \times Re^{-0.2}$$

Heat Transfer Coefficient Calculation

$$m_1 = (\text{hot water})$$

$$m_2 = (\text{cold water})$$

Fig. 3 Basic Representation of Counter Current Flow

$$Q_1 = m_1 \times C_p \times (T_3 - T_4)$$

$$Q_2 = m_2 \times C_p \times (T_2 - T_1)$$

$$Q_{avg} = (Q_1 + Q_2)/2$$

$$\%diff = (Q_1 - Q_2) \times 100 / Q_{avg}$$

$$L.M.T.D. = \{(T_4 - T_1) - (T_3 - T_2)\} / \ln \{(T_4 - T_1) / (T_3 - T_2)\}$$

$$A_i = \pi \times d_i \times L_h$$

$$U_i = Q / (A_i \times LMTD)$$

Fig. 4 : Relationship between Viscosity & Temperature

$$\mu = 10^{-11} \times T^4 - 5 \times 10^{-09} \times T^3 + 7 \times 10^{-07} \times T^2 - 5 \times 10^{-05} \times T + 0.0018$$

$$\text{Where, } T = (T_1 + T_2)/2$$

$$Re = 4 \times m / (\pi \times d_i \times \mu)$$

Fig. 5 : Relationship between Pr & Temperature

$$Pr = 10^{-07} \times T^4 - 4 \times 10^{-05} \times T^3 + 0.0062 \times T^2 - 0.4134T + 13.28$$

$$\frac{1}{U_i} = \frac{1}{h_i} + \frac{d_i}{d_o \times h_o} + \frac{X_w \times d_i}{k_w \times dL} + R_m$$

This reduces to

$$\frac{1}{U_i} = \frac{1}{(h_i)_{exp}} + K = \frac{1}{c(Re)^{0.8}} + K$$

K is to be found from the Wilson Chart as the intercept on the y-axis

Fig. 6 : Wilson chart for twisted tape insert

$$1/h_a = (1/U_i) - K$$

Fig. 7 : Relationship between k_w and Temperature

$$k_w = -9 \times 10^{-6} \times T^2 + 0.0021 T + 0.5568 = 0.6161 \text{ W/m}^2\text{C (at } T = 32.9^\circ\text{C)}$$

$$h_o = 0.023 \times Re^{0.8} \times Pr^{0.4} \times (k/d_i)$$

$$R1 = h_a / h_o$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From Fig. 5.1 it is observed that h_i (expt) and h_i (theo) are almost the same in turbulent region. It is also found that from Fig. 5.2, Nu increases with an increase in Re.

Fig 8 Heat Transfer Coefficient

Fig.5.2 shows the comparison of the Nu obtained from the experimental values for the stationary inner tube for the pipes having pitch of the helical fins 17 mm and 14 mm. The graph shows that, the Nu for the tube having pitch of the helical fins 14 mm is higher than that of 17 mm. Due to the reduction of pitch, the hydraulic diameter decreases and the velocity of fluid increases so that the heat transfer rate increases. The Nu increases by about 40% for the pitch reduction from 17 to 14 mm.

Fig. 9 Nusselt Number

The Fig.5.3 show the comparison of Nu for the different speeds of the inner tubes. The speed of inner tube is varied from 0 rpm to 300 rpm. The graph shows that as the speed of rotation increases, the Nu increases for the same Re value. Due to rotation the velocity of fluid increases so that the turbulence in the fluid increases which results into increase in the heat transfer rate and Nusselt number. After certain speed Nu starts decreasing because fluid gets higher velocity and it start skidding on tube, also less time will be available for heat transfer.

Fig. 10 Graph of Reynolds Vs Nusselt number for the tube having pitch of fins 17 mm at different speeds of rotation

CONCLUSIONS

- ❖ The experimental values of h are compared with that of obtained from standard Dittus-Boelter equation. The graphs show that, as Re increases h increases.
- ❖ Comparing experimental and Dittus-Boelter values of heat transfer coefficient it finds that the difference between these two values goes on increasing with Reynolds number because at higher flow rate less time is available for heat transfer.
- ❖ At higher speed fluid starts skidding so Nu starts decreasing.

NOMENCLATURE:-

- ❖ A_i -Inside heat transfer surface area, m^2
- ❖ A_c -Cross sectional area, m^2

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- ❖ C_p -Specific heat of fluid, J/kg K
- ❖ d_i -Inside diameter of the tube, m
- ❖ Gz - Graetz number, dimensionless
- ❖ h -Difference in level of CCl_4 in the manometer, m
- ❖ h_i -Inside htc, $W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ h_a -(expt) Experimental inside htc, $W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ h_i -(theo) Theoretical inside htc, $W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ h_o -Heat transfer coefficient for smooth tube, $W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ h_a -Augmented value of heat transfer coefficient, $W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ H - Linear distance of the tape for 180° rotation, m.
- ❖ k_w -Thermal conductivity of the tube wall, $w / m \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ L_h -Heat transfer length, m
- ❖ L.M.T.D- Log mean temperature difference, K
- ❖ m -Mass flow rate, kg/s
- ❖ Nu -Nusselt number, dimensionless
- ❖ Pr -Prandtl number, dimensionless
- ❖ ΔP -Pressure drop, N/m^2
- ❖ Q -Heat transfer rate, W
- ❖ Re -Reynolds number
- ❖ $R1$ - Performance evaluation criteria (ratio of augmented value of heat transfer coefficient to smooth tube heat transfer coefficient i.e., h_a/h_o), Dimensionless
- ❖ T -Temperature in $^\circ C$
- ❖ U_i -Overall htc based on the inside surface area, $W / m^2 \cdot ^\circ C$
- ❖ V -Velocity of water, m/s
- ❖ W_t - Weight of water taken, kg
- ❖ *Greek letters*
- ❖ ρ - Fluid density in kg/m^3

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